

THE ROLE OF FUN AND GAMES IN THE LESSONS

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Abstract: Research has shown that games are essential for healthy development in early childhood and beyond. Play lets children practise what they know and also what they don't. It allows them to experiment through trial and error, find solutions to problems, work out the best strategies, and build new confidence and skills.

Key words: practical skills, capability, competition, creative, motivation.

Tips for Successfully Using Games as a Teaching Strategy. Choose Games Suitable for Age, Ability, and Classroom Equipment, Confirm the Usefulness of Curriculum Integration, Provide Clear Goals and Instructions Before Gameplay, Offer Support and Guidance During Gameplay, Follow Up Game Play With Discussion, Memory – There are many video games that require you to remember information, patterns, clues, and more as part of the gameplay. Because of the need to retain critical pieces of information, these games help players improve their memory skills, which can directly translate to improved learning capabilities.

The role of fun and games in the lessons. “By ‘fun and games’ I mean all those activities that we loosely think of as involving play and enjoyment. Singing, clapping hands, chanting rhymes, solving puzzles, drawing, coloring, model-making, games.” It is evident that young learners learn through play much easier and they enjoy it more. This is quite a natural way for them to learn.

They play and love to play. In playing together we can see elements of interaction and during interacting the learners develop language skills. Learning can be absorbed really well. Quite often the learners do not realize they are learning. Fun and games should have an important role in the children’s education. The language learnt by heart can often be a part of the activities. For example, commands for the games can be remembered quite easily. Many games can be looked at as drill exercises but they have an added fun and competition element. For example, a game that works like this is well-known game “Simon says”. What is a game? “A game is played when one or more players compete or co-operate for play offs according to a set of rules”.

“A true game is one that frees the spirit. It allows of no cares but those fictitious ones engendered by the game itself...” Games are activities with rules and goals. Khan states that the achievement of these goals signals the end of the game. Children are very often concerned with controlling whether everybody follows the rules and whether they are not broken. It is obvious that the games need to be motivating. “ For young learners, motivation deriving from the factors outside the classroom, such as parental and social attitudes, is likely to be weaker than that created by events in the classroom itself. Children need to be involved and even excited in order to learn effectively.” Games may focus on oral or written part of the language, they offer a vast selection of activities. Language can also be picked as a result of an enjoyable activity. “Telling stories to students can result in natural language acquisition on their part.” Teachers can tell stories the learners are familiar with in their own language. Then the learners are able to follow it better. Again, the stories need to be picked carefully, the levels of the learners need to be considered and

the teacher has to investigate time into preparation. Teachers can come up with a simple version of the story. Appreciated story can be The Story of the Big Enormous Turnip. Several activities can allow and involve more creative use of the language. New sentences and activities can be produced by the children themselves. Songs are most grateful way forth is. The learners can make up new verses, then they can be extended. Example - a song “This is the way, I ...” or “If you are happy and you know it...”.

As said above games and fun are important parts of the lesson. A play is in the essential nature of the child. There are many possibilities for adapting games we can find. The teachers should not forget the values of games and fun activities in the lessons. All this can be applied to teaching vocabulary too. Teachers can “play” with vocabulary while teaching it. It is very appreciated by the learners.

Although some teachers of English see language games as time consumers or classroom techniques for fun, games have a special role in any foreign language teaching programmer because they facilitate foreign language learning especially for young learners. With the introduction of communicative language teaching, English language teaching and learning has become much more demanding for teachers and learners just like any other innovation poses challenges for its users.

Studies show that playing games in the classroom can increase overall motivation. Students become more motivated to learn, pay attention, and participate in-class activities. What is the purpose of games? Games generally involve mental or physical stimulation, and often both. Many games help develop practical skills, serve as a form of exercise, or otherwise perform an educational, simulational, or psychological role.

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